

The spectra of the transition metal chelates of tetradentate Schiff bases obtained by the condensation of acetylacetone and ethylenediamine or propylenediamide consist of a band at $\sim 1120\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which has unequivocally been assigned to the stretching vibration of C—O linkage in the metal chelate ring¹¹. When the complex ligand acts as Lewis bases towards tin(II) halides or isothiocyanate, the spectra of the resulting products show little change in the position of this absorption, thereby suggesting only a weak coordination of tin(II) with the diketo-imine transition metal complex ligands. The conclusion is supported by the reported observations that the triple coordination occurs more readily *via* phenolic oxygen rather than diketo-imine oxygen^{4,12,13}.

The $\nu_{\text{Sn-O}}$ occurs over an exceptionally wide range of frequency depending upon the nature of bonding between the two atoms. In the present investigation, the coordination of tin(II) moieties with the phenolic or alcoholic oxygen (metal diketoimine ring oxygen) is supported by the appearance of a band at $\sim 600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is absent in the spectra of the corresponding complex ligands. Similar assignment have been made in case of tin(II) chelates^{14,15} and organotin(IV) halide adducts with Salen¹⁶ and M Salen¹⁷. The Sn—Cl and Sn—Br stretching vibrations could not be identified since they lie beyond the recorded range of the spectra.

NCS absorption: In the present investigation the splitting of the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ absorptions in the ir of the solid adducts in the range of 2148-2000 and 860-800 cm^{-1} , respectively indicates the presence of two crystallographically distinct thiocyanate groups N-bonded to the metal atom. The results are in good agreement with reported data for tin(II) isothiocyanate^{7,18} and their adducts with some O-N-donor ligands¹⁹.

On the basis of the foregoing discussion it is evident that transition metal chelates of tetradentate bases derived from salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone or acetylacetone and diamines form molecular adducts of 1:1 stoichiometry with tin(II) chloride, bromide and isothiocyanate. The newly synthesised coordination compounds contain two triply bonded oxygen atoms. The tin(II) halides behave primarily as monofunctional acceptor although empty d-orbitals are available for additional bonding. The following probable structure of the complexes involving four coordinated tin(II) atom in combination with the bidentate complex ligand could not be made with certainty owing to the

insolubility of the compounds in common organic solvents which restricted studies in solution and also due to the lack of facilities for X-ray analysis.

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Reaction of Lead Tetraacetate with Cholest-5-ene and Its 3 β -Substituted Derivatives

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MIHAILOVIC *et al.*¹ synthesised 7-acetoxyated derivative from the reaction of lead tetraacetate with 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene. But it has been

observed² that when lead tetraacetate is used along with potassium acetate, the double bond gets affected and lactones are produced as major products. In order to synthesise steroidal lactones by lead tetraacetate, we undertook the studies on cholest-5-ene (1) and 3 β -chlorocholest-5-ene (2). The former substrate yielded an abnormal product 6 α -carboxymethylcholest-4-ene (5) and the latter afforded 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene (6), a known compound. The structures of these compounds were established on the basis of their spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded in nujol with a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra were run in CDCl_3 by a Varian A60 instrument with TMS as internal standard. Mass spectrum was obtained on a JEOL JMSD 300 instrument using direct insertion technique at an ionisation energy of 70 eV. Light petroleum refers to the fraction of b.p. 60-80°. Nmr values are given in ppm (s=singlet, d=doublet, t=triplet, mc=multiplet centered at, $W_{\frac{1}{2}}$ =half band width).

Reaction of cholest-5-ene (1) with lead tetraacetate : Compound 1 (1 g) was dissolved in warm acetic acid (50 ml) and anhydrous potassium acetate (10 g) was added followed by the addition of equimolar quantity of lead tetraacetate. The mixture was heated under reflux for 30 h in anhydrous condition. After the completion of reaction the mixture was diluted with water and compound was extracted from ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and water successively and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent gave an oil which was chromatographed over silica gel (20 g). Elution with light petroleum gave unreacted compound 1. Further elution with light petroleum-ether (30:1) afforded a white compound (5), recrystallised from acetone (0.75 g), m.p. 158° (Found: C, 81.33; H, 11.24. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 81.34; H, 11.25%) M^+ 428; ν_{max} 3250 (OH), 1700 (-CO-OH), 1645 (C=C) and 1290 cm^{-1} (C-O); δ 11.36 (unresolved s, COOH exchangeable with D_2O), 5.4 (t, C_4 -H vinylic), 2.75 (mc, C_6 - α H, $W_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 14 Hz, axial)², 2.45 (d, CH_2 -COOH), 1.20 (s, C_{10} - CH_3), 1.05 (s, C_{18} - CH_3), 0.99 and 0.87 (other methyl protons).

Reaction of 3 β -chlorocholest-5-ene (2) with lead tetraacetate : The reaction of compound 2 (1 g) was

performed with equimolar quantity of lead tetraacetate under similar conditions. The ethereal layer obtained after work-up was evaporated to dryness and an oil thus obtained was crystallised from acetone to get pure 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene (6) (0.90 g), m.p. 115° (lit.⁴ 116°); ν_{max} 1720 (CH_3 -CO-O), 1640 (C=C) and 1210 cm^{-1} (C-O); δ 5.4 (mc, C_4 -H vinylic), 4.61 (mc, C_3 - α H, $W_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 16 Hz, axial), 1.97 (s, CH_3 -CO-O), 1.2 (s, C_{10} - CH_3), 1.0 (s, C_{18} - CH_3), 0.98 and 0.88 (other methyl protons).

Discussion

Characterisation of compound 5 as 6 α -carboxymethylcholest-4-ene : The compound 5, m.p. 158° analysed for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$ showed bands at 3250 (OH), 1700 (-CO-OH) and 1645 cm^{-1} (C=C) in its ir spectrum. In its ^1H nmr spectrum an unresolved singlet at δ 11.36 for one proton exchangeable with D_2O indicated the presence of carboxyl group. A doublet at δ 2.45 integrated for two protons is ascribable to methylene group which serves as side chain attached on C_6 and on which carboxyl group is connected. Multiplets at δ 2.75 ($W_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 14 Hz) for C_6 - β H (axial) and at 5.4 for C_4 -H (vinylic) are thus ascribed. The structure was corroborated by mass spectrum which exhibited molecular ion peak at M^+ 428 (50.09%). The diagnostic peak is obtained at m/z 95 (36.6%) which signifies the elimination of ring A. A strong peak at m/z 41 (50.11%) supports the formation of fragment m/z 95. The mode of fragmentation is given in Scheme 1. The

Scheme 1

other important peaks are at m/z 413 (M^+ CH_3 , 35.49%), m/z 369 (M^+ CH_3 -COOH, 19.60%) and m/z 315 (M^+ C_8H_{17} , 14.70%).

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Synthesis and Mass Spectra of Some 2H-Pyrano(2,3-b)quinolin-2-ones

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2H-Pyrano(2,3-b)quinolin-2-ones are of interest in that they are linear benzaza analogues of coumarins which have gained considerable importance because of their biological and chemical properties¹. As very little work^{2,3} has been done earlier on the synthesis of 2H-pyrano(2,3-b)quinolin-2-ones, a scheme of synthesis of these compounds was undertaken. The present work describes the synthesis of some new 2H-pyrano(2,3-b)quinolin-2-ones and their mass spectral fragmentation including that of the parent one. 3-Formyl-2-quinolones (2a-f), which may be considered as benzaza analogues of salicylaldehyde were taken as starting materials and were obtained by the acid hydrolysis of 2-chloro-3-formylquinolines (1a-f), which in turn were prepared according to the procedure described in literature⁴. 3-Formyl-2-quinolones (2a-f) were then condensed with malonic acid under the conditions of Knoevenagel reaction when 3-(2-oxo-1,2-dihydro-3-quinolyl)acrylic acids (3a-f) were obtained in 78-82% yield. The acrylic acids (3a-f) were then cyclised by employing polyphosphoric acid as cyclising agent and the desired 2H-pyrano(2,3-b)quinolin-2-ones (4a-f) were obtained in yields varying from 69 to 95% (Scheme 1).

Pyranoquinolines (4a-f) exhibit very characteristic pmr spectra. The protons at positions 3 and 4 appear as sharp doublets (J 10 Hz) in the region of δ 6.7-6.9 and 8.25-8.5, respectively, and proton at position 5 appears as a singlet in the region of δ 9-9.4. The signals due to the aromatic protons and methoxyl protons appear in the expected regions.

Mass spectra of the pyranoquinolines (4a-d) are also determined. All show intense molecular ion peak as one would expect of this aromatic system. Compounds 4a and 4b also show half mass peaks corresponding to the doubly charged molecular ion.

Scheme 1

In each case a peak is exhibited at M-28 owing to the loss of CO, characteristic of pyrones. Since the subsequent decomposition of M-CO is similar to that of furo(2,3-b)quinoline, it might be reasonably inferred, on the lines of the fragmentation of benzofuran⁵ as shown for the parent compound 4a in Scheme 2. The ion m/e 140, may possibly have a structure corresponding to benzodehydro-tropilium ion. In case of 4d fragments corresponding to ³⁷Cl isotope are also observed.

Scheme 2

Experimental

Hydrolysis of 2-chloro-3-formylquinolines (1a-f): A mixture of 2-chloro-3-formylquinoline (0.0104 M) and aqueous hydrochloric acid (35 ml; 4 M) was heated under reflux for 1 h, and then allowed to cool to room temperature. After 1 h the reaction mixture was poured on to crushed ice, when 3-formyl-2-quinolone separated as a yellow solid. It was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from aqueous acetic acid. M.p., yield, ir and analytical data of 2a-f are given in Table 1.